

METAL/METAL COMPOSITES FOR AUTOMOTIVE COMPONENTS

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ABSTRACT

The concept of composite materials is attractive for car manufacturers. During the past several years, much work has been conducted on ceramic reinforced metal matrix composites, but today commercial applications are still very limited. This led us to develop metal/metal composites which appear very promising for structural automotive applications in the next future, especially because of the lower costs of metallic reinforcements as compared to ceramic ones. The most appropriate processing method is the melt infiltration by squeeze casting on conditions that several vital points be solved in order to succeed. The manufacturing of the fibrous metallic preform must be compatible with mass production and casting process must allow complete infiltration. The interface between the reinforcement and the Al-alloy matrix must be strong to allow load transfer and good mechanical properties; thereby, the interfacial phenomena taking place during casting have to be controlled and limited by adequate alloying additions. Ni and Cr additions in ferrous alloy fibres as Si and Cu additions in aluminium baths are found to reduce the growth of interfacial phases while Zn additions increase the rate of reaction. It is shown that stainless steel short fibre (30 vol%) reinforced aluminium matrix composites have tensile strength over three to four that of the aluminium matrix.

KEYWORDS : Metal matrix composites ; metallic fibrous reinforcement ; squeeze casting ; aluminium matrix ; interfacial reactions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, car manufacturers take more and more interest in composite materials. This interest is obvious for organic matrix composites which are considered as promising materials by the designers and, to a lesser extent, for metal matrix composites which are the purpose of the present paper. This class of materials presents a potential for the mechanical parts of cars for which some properties are needed : lightening, strength, rigidity, heat resistance, wear resistance, fatigue resistance at high temperature, low thermal expansion coefficient, low electrical and thermal conductivity in some cases ; these requests must provide customer with high performances, low consumption, low cost, reliability and comfort (e.g., less noise). In this way, the weight reduction of moving parts (piston, connecting rod, crankshaft) or of non-moving parts (e.g., suspension arm, differential case, brake disc), the improvement of heat resistance of combustion chambers are expected to be achieved by using reinforced aluminium alloys. Because several essential

problems including costs, mass-production techniques, mechanical properties have not yet been solved, automotive parts made of metal matrix composites are still nowadays very limited. In fact, it is thought that the development of such materials suffered in past years from irrational requests : the materials had to be stiffer, stronger, tougher with improved elevated temperature capability and low costs.

This paper deals with the use and the processing of metal matrix composites reinforced by metallic fibres. First, the authors express their view on the concept of composite material applied to automotive components. Then, the possible methods of metal/metal composite processing are described. Finally, the various strategical aspects taken into account during the squeeze casting infiltration process are discussed and illustrated by examples.

2. THE CONCEPT OF COMPOSITE

A composite material consists of "phases" having the ability to modify the behaviour of the matrix within which they are properly distributed ; the "phases" bonded to the matrix have particular microstructural arrangements and morphologies in order to achieve optimum properties. In this way, the composite appears as a custom designed material, adjustable to the required properties or applications. Considering this concept, microstructures with diverse combinations of properties can be achieved by selection of reinforcements as for example, hard phases for strength, ductile phases for toughness and whiskers for creep resistance. Of course, the concept is an utopia of engineer if economical aspects and technical needs are not taken into account.

Aeronautic, aerospace and military applications have provided the main driving force for the development of metal matrix composites that goes back to the early 1960's (1). Much work has been carried out on aluminium-based materials reinforced by boron and carbon fibres ; however, their high manufacturing costs are a barrier to a large scale use. The enthusiasm for reinforcing metals was revived in the 1980's with the development of ceramic fibres (2-3) ; composites such as Al/SiC whiskers, Al/SiC fibre and Al/Al₂O₃ fibre expected to achieve lighening and rigidity, were of interest for automotive industry. The first commercial outcome was proposed by Toyota (4) who developed a piston made of alumina fibre reinforced Al-alloy for a diesel engine ; the wear resistance of the reinforced area was enhanced. Unfortunately, car manufacturers were mistaken by directly choosing these materials instead of developing new ones better suited to automotive needs. As a consequence, the applications for automotive parts are today very poor because ceramic fibres and composite processing methods are expensive and not consistent with a mass production. This has driven the developers toward casting processes with cheapest ceramic particulate composites (e.g., SiC, Al₂O₃) as reinforcements (5). However, such composites also have lowest properties and their potential applications are mainly wear resistance, thermal stability and reduction of thermal dilatation coefficient. Other recent developments consist in using hybrid reinforcements in metal matrix composites. As an example, for automotive applications, ceramic fibres (Al₂O₃-SiO₂) and NiAl₃ intermetallic particles distributed in an Al-alloy matrix have been found to improve strongly wear and seizure properties of pistons (6). Our view is that intermetallic reinforcements appear very promising in the next future for the development of new composite materials.

In order to succeed and to appreciate the composite concept, the immediate challenge is to choose matrices, reinforcements and production techniques making the composites suitable for the automotive industry. Moreover, the composite material must fulfil an overall technological problem rather than a single criterion. Therefore, the aims to achieve and the main benefits to be

expected from the composites must be less ambitious. This led us presently to pay attention to metallic reinforcements that appear attractive and promising for many reasons :

- various manufacturing processes are available for metal fibres (melt overflow, melt extraction, wire drawing),
- various types of metal fibres can be found at lesser costs than ceramic fibres (e.g., Al_2O_3 : 1200 \$/dm³, stainless steel : 160 \$/dm³, steel : 40 \$/dm³),
- good properties of fibres can be obtained relatively easily by adding adequate elements,
- coating methods on metal fibres to improve the bonding with the matrix can be easily carried out ,
- metal/metal interactions are better understood than metal/ceramic interactions,
- although the inherent weight of metal fibres is higher than that of ceramic fibres, the ductility of metal fibres may give potential improvement of toughness in composites.

Previously, metal/metal composites such as stainless steel long fibre reinforced aluminium alloys prepared by hot pressing methods have been produced (7-9). Results showed that advantages might be obtained from these composites : good strength, resistance to fatigue-crack propagation, reduction of creep rate, good stress intensity values (K_{Ic}). For example, strengths as high as 1500 MPa were obtained in the direction parallel to the fibre and resistance to crack propagation was found very good with K_{Ic} values more than 240 MPa \sqrt{m} at a volume fraction of 40% (9). More recent studies have been carried out on such composites prepared by melt infiltration techniques (10-11). It seems that improved properties may also be expected with short metal fibres if the aspect ratio is sufficiently high. As regards practical applications, Honda (12) produced by squeeze casting a connecting rod in reinforced Al-alloy ; the reinforcement localized to the core consisted of 45 vol% unidirectional stainless steel fibres and led to 30 % weight reduction.

Lastly, the development of new composite materials must take account of the overall past experience on metal matrix composites and of various aspects of company commitment such as :

- technical aspects (nature, level and volume of knowledge in each step of the new automotive component, perturbations induced by a particular solution on the overall component function...)
- economical aspects (magnitude of investments, global effectiveness of the new solution)
- human aspects (composite concept promotion for complete commitment of designing, manufacturing engineering, production, purchase, trade and quality departments).

From this point of view, the development of metal/metal composites instead of ceramic reinforced metal matrix composites appears to be the best compromise in regard to the forementioned criteria and the most promising way for structural automotive applications in the next future.

3. GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PROCESSING OF METAL/METAL COMPOSITES

Composite processing methods can be classified according to the form in which the matrix is introduced (13) and thus, according to the physicochemical aspects involved during the preparation. In the case of solid-matrix methods, solid state diffusion and plastic deformation phenomena are mainly involved in order to achieve the bonding between the matrix and the reinforcement. Processes such as extrusion, sintering, hot isostatic pressing, diffusion bonding...can be used. However, most of them are not well suited for automotive manufacturing because of their expensive costs. Molten matrix methods appear more realistic for industrial applications

requiring high production rates and low costs. The major production routes concern essentially either melt infiltration through fibrous preforms or introduction of solid particles and short fibres into melts.

Briefly, the preparation of composites by directly introducing metal particles into a molten mother alloy consists in obtaining a uniform dispersion of the particles by mixing them without being dissolved away in the matrix. As the interfacial phenomena play an important role, this process needs strategies to avoid deterioration of particles. As an example, Al-Ni and Al-Si-Cu base alloys which offer superior wear resistance by dispersion of Ni particles have been produced by such a technique (14). In order to improve strength resistance, a better load transfer must be obtained ; therefore, metal fibres sufficiently short and thin to avoid casting problems have to be used. Unfortunately, as their cost is higher, the interest of this process is reduced. Thus, the melt infiltration processes appear more promising for automotive components and, among them, the squeeze casting infiltration process presents many advantages which will be recalled in the next section. One of them is the near-net shape capability which is interesting from an economical point of view : because the cost of casting composites is generally increased by that of reinforcements, the machining known to be expensive has to be decreased. A major limitation of this process is in the range and in the size of parts that can be cast (very thin pieces are not desirable because of early solidification), also pieces with cores are difficult to cast.

In order to succeed in producing the composite by melt infiltration, the following vital points must be overcome : (i) the fibrous preform preparation, (ii) the matrix/reinforcement interface formation, (iii) the predicting behaviour of composites. We will examine very briefly the last point, the others being developed in section 4.

The behaviour of composites has to be well understood (e.g., mechanical and thermal properties). Considering the hugeness of possible reinforcement/matrix combinations, a numerical simulation approach rather than an experimental one seems to be more relevant as regards the different constraints involved by composite microstructure designing. Different tools such as finite element and finite difference methods are available, but both the software and numerical basic level necessary to be able to use them and the required computer capability, lead to prefer simpler methods implementable on personal computers with a near elementary metallurgical knowledge. Homogenization technics are powerful from this point of view. The main principle of these technics is to find the equivalent fictitious homogeneous material which has the same behaviour as the actual composite one. For linear behaviours (e.g. linear elasticity and thermoelasticity, thermal and electrical conductivities, matter transport, etc...), different models checked by experiments are usable. Their use requires a minimal amount of informations concerning the behaviour, the average shape and orientation, and the volume fraction of each phase to allow a prediction of the effective composite behaviour (15-16) ; moreover, reinforcement/matrix interaction or thick interface layer can be taken into account. For non linear behaviour such as plasticity, viscoelasticity and fracture, the mathematical treatments become more difficult and need an increase of the microstructure information amount. Nevertheless, for uniaxial traction, elastic numerical scheme can be kept if tangential modulus instead of elastic ones are chosen for computation (16). The interest of such predictive tools is shown as an example in table 1 which presents a comparison between calculated and experimental values in the case of Al_2O_3 particles reinforced 2024 Al-alloys, the predicted values are calculated using various analytical methods. In the present case, a good agreement is observed.

Al ₂ O ₃ * Volume Fraction in 2024** %	Young Modulus Reuss Bound GPa	Young Modulus Hashin Lower Bound GPa	Young Modulus Hervé Zaoui Model GPa	Experimental Composite Young Modulus (Duralcan Data)GPa	Young Modulus Hashin Upper Bound GPa	Young Modulus Voigt Bound Gpa
10	79.5	83.4	83.4	84.1	91.8	103
15	83.1	89.6	90.0	91.7	102	118
20	87.1	96.0	96.4	101	112	133

* YM(Al₂O₃)=370GPa, Poisson's Ratio(Al₂O₃)= 0.27

**YM(2024)=73GPa, Poisson's Ratio(2024)= 0.30

TABLE 1. Calculated and experimental Young Modulus values for Al₂O₃ reinforced 2024 Al-alloy (Al-Cu-Mg).

4. PROCESSING OF METAL/METAL COMPOSITES BY SQUEEZE CASTING INFILTRATION

Metal fibre preforms are infiltrated with molten metal (Al-alloys) by means of squeeze casting process. In this process, solidification takes place under a high pressure which is several orders of magnitude greater than the melt pressure developed in conventional foundry practice. The various aspects of the squeeze casting process are reviewed in several papers (17-18). In addition to relatively high solidification rates which significantly reduce the fibre/matrix contact time, casting quality is enhanced by the collapse of gas and shrinkage porosity under the influence of the pressure. Besides, the advantages of this process include simplicity, speed of operation and near-net shape capability as above-mentioned.

We present here the main aspects which have to be considered to guarantee successful processing of metal/metal composites.

4.1 Preform manufacturing

The metal fibres must be packaged in order to make preforms to the desired shape and to consolidate them to allow the handling. This step is difficult but has to be solved and to be compatible with mass production otherwise the composite is bound to fail. Various techniques are available to prepare strong enough preforms (e.g., sintering); they consist essentially in forming connections between fibres. Fibres can be distributed either randomly (isotropic properties) or orientated (anisotropic properties). In all cases, even distribution of fibres is required in order not to impair mechanical properties by penetration defects and by inhomogeneities in fibre volume fraction. Moreover, the preform structure must allow complete infiltration i.e., the melt must penetrate the narrow gaps in the contact zones between fibres. This is particularly important in the case of aligned fibre composites. Usually, the fibre separation can be achieved by hybridising the composite (addition of fine particulate material (19)).

4.2 Preform infiltration

In practice, the preheated preform is fixed into a preheated die casting, a measured quantity of melt alloy is poured into the die and a ram applies pressure during solidification forcing liquid metal to penetrate within the interstitial spaces of the fibrous preform. During this step, several complicated fundamental phenomena take place such as hydrodynamics (capillarity effects, viscosity of the liquid), physicochemical effects between the fibre and matrix (mutual solubility, diffusion, chemical reactions,

intermetallic compound formation) and thermal phenomena (exothermic reactions, solidification, heat transfer). They are of importance because they influence infiltration kinetics and the resulting composite microstructure.

During infiltration step, liquid metal has first to penetrate the preform, and thence capillary effects which act to promote or impede infiltration may be of significance. It is recalled that the capillary pressure i.e., the pressure set up by the liquid in capillary environments is given by $P = 2\Gamma \cos \theta / r$ (Γ : surface energy at the liquid-vapor interface, r : curvature at the molten metal front, θ : wetting angle of the liquid metal on the fibre). Then, frictional forces resulting from the viscosity of the liquid metal can impede the progress of the metal through the interfibre channels. Another phenomenon that requires consideration is freeze choking or premature solidification of the advancing liquid which modifies the effective capillary diameter. Lastly, the entrapped gas in the preform is a source of resistance to infiltration and, if the gaseous phase quantity is not negligible, convective heat may occur then developing temperature gradients. As the forementioned effects preclude full melt penetration, energy in the form of external pressure must be supplied ; thereby, the squeeze casting process is appropriate. These points are more developed in a forthcoming publication (20). Briefly, it appears that complete penetration for wetting and non-wetting systems is achieved with very low excess pressure (≈ 1 MPa) if isothermal conditions are fulfilled and if trapped gas are evacuated. As a consequence, the failure of the melt to penetrate a preform results of the competition between hydrodynamics (filling) and thermal effects (heat transfer).

Concerning thermal effects, the most important parameters are mold preheat, preform preheat and melt superheat temperatures. In casting processes, these are usually all different from one another. The fibres are often initially held at a temperature significantly lower than that of the liquid metal, and heat can flow locally from liquid metal to fibres when the two phases come in contact and more generally between the composite and its surroundings. As a result of heat exchange, solid metal can form along the mold wall and then in the interfibre region where both liquid and solid metal coexist. The effect of thermal losses ahead the infiltration front due to external heat extraction leads the liquid flow to be stopped when sufficient solidification occurs to close flow channels. Therefore, the infiltration velocity has to be reasonably high (10 to 100 mm/s) to overcome these effects.

As regards wetting of solid metal surfaces by molten metals, research was mainly stimulated in the 1950's by brazing and soldering (21-23). These works are reviewed and discussed by the present authors in another publication (24). It appears that non-wetting in metal/metal systems is observed only in the case of the presence of an oxide film on the substrate. In addition, wetting is generally related to mutual solubility and intermetallic formation. More precisely, wetting due to pure capillary effects appears at the very short contact time between the liquid and solid (less than 1 second) ; afterwards, the alloying energy becomes the driving force for the flow of the liquid metal.

4.3 Fibre/matrix interactions

When a solid metal is brought into contact with a liquid metal, the following phenomena take place simultaneously at the interface : dissolution of the solid into the liquid, formation and growth of a transition zone made of intermetallic compounds by migration of the molten metal into the solid (25-26). The thickness of the intermediate zone is therefore dependent on the dissolution kinetics controlled by the nature of mass transfer of the components in the liquid (diffusion or convection) and on the growth

kinetics of the interfacial phases. Briefly, the mechanisms controlling the rate during the interlayer growth are the atomic diffusion of the reacting species through the interlayer and the interface chemical reaction, the observed rate being determined by the rate of the slowest process. Two separate kinetics laws are obeyed in these two mechanisms : the thickness of the interlayer increases in accordance with a parabolic law if diffusion is the rate controlling step and with a linear law in the interface reaction controlling case. It appears that the thickness of intermetallic phases is reduced for slow solid state diffusion and high dissolution rate.

In many instances, the formation of brittle intermetallic layered phases can lead to a reduction in desirable mechanical and physical properties ; in consequence, their thickness must be as small as possible and interaction conditions must be used to prevent their growth. This can be achieved by reducing contact time between the fibre and matrix (the squeeze casting process is favorable), by modifying diffusion coefficients with adequate additions in fibres and melt matrix and by using adequate coatings as diffusion barriers. Moreover, excessive formation of intermetallic compounds is undesirable because liquid flow may become more difficult as particles removed from the fibres may accumulate thus increasing viscosity, and as gaps between fibres become smaller. However, one may take advantage of the intermetallic formation which is generally exothermic ; because of heat production, the solidification of metal in the interfibre region can be reduced and infiltration improved.

As examples, the effect of alloying additions (Cr, Ni) to fibres in ferrous alloys has been investigated at 700 C in the case of low mild steel and stainless steel (Fe-18Cr-8Ni) rods exposed for various times to an unsaturated melt aluminium. In both cases, the solid/liquid interaction leads to the formation of two intermetallic phases (Figure 1) : the $FeAl_3$ phase is found adjacent to the steel (layer I) and the Fe_2Al_7 phase is found adjacent to the aluminium (layer II). However, the morphology and thickness of these phases are different. The tongue-like structure of layer I in the case of mild steel disappears by additions of Cr and Ni, layer II appears also more porous ; moreover, the thickness of layer I is strongly reduced with stainless steel. In other words, the interlayer morphology is more regular when its growth rate is lowered by Cr and Ni additions. It is generally observed that silicon additions in an aluminium bath result in a decrease of the $FeAl_y$ -type intermetallic layer thickness, and the serrated nature of the steel/intermetallic layer interface becomes a planar one (27). The effect of other alloying additions is often conflicting and for example copper additions can increase or decrease the layer growth depending on authors. Our recent work carried out on the immersion of steel rods into Al-5Si-3Cu-0.3Mg baths shows a strong reduction of the interlayer thickness (Figure 2). Reversely, the additions of zinc seem to produce a drastic increase in the rate of reaction, this is in agreement with our observations which show that stainless steel fibres were strongly degraded when Al-Zn alloys were used.

4.4 Some results

It is not possible to detail the technology used to prepare the metal/metal composites for confidentiality reasons. Commercial aluminium, aluminium-silicon alloy and age-hardenable aluminium alloy (Al-Zn-Mg-Cu) have been used as matrix materials and 316L type stainless steel short fibres as the reinforcement. Molten infiltration of fibrous preform by squeeze casting process is found to be complete. As reported in § 4.3, microscopic observations revealed that interfacial reactions are more than desirable with the Al-Zn-Mg-Cu matrix. For the other cases, no apparent significant reactions were observed at the interface (Figure 3). Tensile tests conducted at room temperature on composites made of commercial aluminium as matrix and with a fibre volume fraction of 30 percent show a reinforcement effect ;

FIGURE 1. Microstructures of the low mild steel/aluminium interface (A) and of the stainless steel/aluminium interface (B). Immersion conditions : temperature = 700 C, time = 140 s.

FIGURE 2. Microstructure of the interface between low mild steel and Al-5Si-3Cu-0.3Mg after immersion at 700 C for 140 seconds.

these composites have tensile strength (182 MPa) over three to four times that of the matrix (51.4 MPa) cast under the same manufacturing conditions. The surface fracture of such a composite is shown in figure 4.

70 μm

FIGURE 3. Microstructure of an Al-Si alloy matrix reinforced with 316L stainless steel short fibres.

60 μm

FIGURE 4. Surface fracture of a commercial aluminium matrix reinforced with 316L stainless steel short fibres.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Considering the past experience, the development of metal matrix composites must strongly take account of economical and technical aspects to guarantee success ; this means that car manufacturers must develop their own materials well suited to their own needs. From this point of view, the metal/metal composites appear very attractive for automotive components because of the lower costs of metallic reinforcements and of their potential toughness improvement. It appears that the molten infiltration by squeeze casting is the most promising manufacturing technique for these composites. However, vital points must be well controlled such as the manufacture of preforms which must allow large scale production, the infiltration which must be complete to avoid casting defects and the formation of the interface between the matrix and reinforcement which influences the final mechanical properties. The various phenomena taking place at the interface and giving rise to the bonding must be well understood ; adequate coatings or additions in the fibres or in the matrix must be used to reduce the growth rate of the intermetallic compounds. It is shown that stainless steel short fibre reinforced aluminium matrix composites with a fibre volume fraction of 30 percent have a tensile strength three to four times that of the matrix cast under the same conditions. Other works are in progress with different matrices and metallic fibres.

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